

MOTIVATION AMONG PAKISTANI ENGLISH LEARNERS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INTEGRATIVE AND INSTRUMENTAL ORIENTATIONS

Shakir Shahzad^{*1}, Raza-E- Mustafa²

^{*1}PhD Scholar, Department of English, University of Gujrat

²Assistant Professor, Department of English, University of Gujrat

¹25016102-005@uog.edu.pk, ²razaemustafa@uog.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Shakir Shahzad

Abstract

Motivation plays a significant role in second language acquisition. It has widely been studied across the globe. The existing research on motivation, in the postcolonial English-dominant countries like Pakistan, has focused on language policies, English medium schooling, and public attitude towards English language. The current study investigates motivational orientations in BS English students in Pakistan. Explicitly, the study intends to measure the relative strengths of integrative and instrumental orientations, their correlation with self-perceived achievements, and persistence, and the role of familial, cultural, and social influences in shaping motivation. The researcher utilizes Gardner's (1985) socio-educational model of L2 motivation, and Dörnyei's (2005) L2 motivation system. The study uses a mixed-methods survey design. The quantitative data is collected through a structured questionnaire. The qualitative data is collected through open-ended questions. One hundred nineteen students have participated in the study. The quantitative results reveal that the participants have showed generally high levels of motivation across all orientations. Instrumental motivation ($M = 4.14$, $SD = 0.81$), with a little difference, is higher than integrative motivation ($M = 4.06$, $SD = 0.80$). This difference is not statistically significant. Both integrative, and instrumental orientations are found to be positively associated with self-perceived outcomes. The results also highlight noticeable social, cultural, and familial pressures that shape motivational orientations. The qualitative findings complement and confirm the quantitative results. The current study has pedagogical implications in Pakistani context. The classroom environments should amalgamate pragmatic orientations with intrinsic interest. It would result in better learning outcomes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Motivation is a driving force in language acquisition. It is considered an important individual difference factor in language learning. It affects the effort the learners put in, their engagement and persistence, their reactions to challenges and difficulties, and their ultimate attainment in learning a second language (Dörnyei

& Ushioda, 2021). Gardner, in his socio-educational model, defines motivation as a complex blend of attitudes, effort, and the desire to learn an additional language (Gardner, 1985). "Motivation is a complex construct that involves the reasons or goals learners have for learning a second language, the effort they put into learning,

and the attributes they form as a result of their attempts to learn” (Ellis, 2015, p. 50). He explains that motivated learners achieve better results. The research studies in SLA also support this view. The studies show that the learners who have stronger motivation often reach higher levels of proficiency. The learners with more enduring motivation maintain long term engagement with the target language (Dörnyei, 2005). Understanding motivation and the factors influencing it becomes especially more important in the settings where English is learned as a foreign language. In these contexts, the learners have very little contact with the authentic language use beyond the classroom setting (Gardner, 2005).

In the tradition and evolution of motivation, two major theoretical strands have been particularly influential. In the first place, Gardner (1985) presents a sharp contrast between integrative motivation and instrumental motivation. Intrinsic motivation is driven by the inherent interest in the target language. It refers to a learner’s desire to identify with the speakers of the target language and their culture. The learners psychologically feel close to the target language. On the contrary, instrumental motivation is driven by the utilitarian goals. It refers to learning a language for the practical benefits such as passing examinations, securing jobs or getting promotions. The learners secure material and social advantages. Self-Determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000) emphasizes that extrinsic motivation is not always negative. It can rather take a more self-directed form; the learners gradually internalize external goals and values. The second strand is Dörnyei’s (2005) work on individual differences and L2 Motivational System. It views motivation through learner’s future self-images and the social obligations they recognize. These two approaches show that motivation is not simple and fixed. It is multidimensional and dynamic construct that depends on social context (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2021).

The recent accounts of motivation in the field of SLA emphasize its complex and contextual nature. Dörnyei and Ushioda (2021) identify that the motivation of L2 learner is shaped by certain

contextual factors such as global discourses, local education policies, classroom experiences, and personal background. Ellis (1994) also explicates that motivation should be examined in relation to the psychological and broader contextual factors; it should not be treated in isolation as purely an internal trait. According to Ortega (2009), second language acquisition is a socially shaped process where identities and goals of the learners develop over time. It is due to the interaction with institutions, peers, and imagined communities. These perspectives suggest that the studies on integrative motivation and instrumental motivation should consider the particular sociolinguistic context of learning.

Pakistan offers a rich and complex context to study motivation for learning English. English is the co-official language in Pakistan. It holds the highest place in the language hierarchy. It is the language of higher education, judiciary and bureaucracy. The elite employment sectors also use English as medium of communication. English, actually, acts as a gatekeeper for social and economic mobility (Zafar & Ali, 2018). Rahman (2005), in his work on English medium schooling, qualifies English as a “passport to privilege”. He also highlights that access to high quality English instruction varies among social classes and across school types. Fatima, Mustafa and Kousar (2025) believe that motivation plays an important role in Pakistani classroom. Manan, Dumanig, and David (2015) qualify the growing demand of English medium education as an English medium fever. They add that this English medium fever is driven by parental desires, state policies, and market pressure.

In this complex environment, Pakistani learners have many overlapping reasons for learning English. For some learners, it is required for international mobility. This involves prerequisite tests like IELTS, TOEFL, and PTE. For others, English is very important for career growth within Pakistan. In this case, fluent English is linked to competence and modernity. There are some learners who develop integrative orientations. This involves interest in English culture, literature, and global participation. The Pakistani learners of English also face social and familial expectations.

This pressure aligns with Dornyei's (2005) "ought-to L2 self". Moreover, English is also a postcolonial legacy in Pakistan.

Although English is a central language in Pakistan, yet research on L2 motivation is limited. The existing research studies have focused on school level learners, and they are related to the debates about medium of instruction and language policies. There is less work on university level students, particularly those majoring in English. There remains a gap how university level majors understand their own reasons, integrative or instrumental, for learning English. Little is known about how their motivations are shaped by social, cultural, and familial pressures, and how their motivations relate to their self-perceived progress and to their long term involvement.

The present study aims to examine motivational orientations among BS English students in Pakistan. The researcher utilizes two complementary theories: Gardner's (1985) socio-educational model of L2 motivation and Dornyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System. Explicitly, the current study, drawing on Gardner's distinction between integrative and instrumental motivation, explores the stronger motivational orientation among the learners. It seeks to determine which type of motivation relates more strongly to the learners' self-reported effort, persistence, and perceived achievement. In addition to this, the study, informed by Dornyei's ought-to L2 self, investigates the role of social, cultural, and familial pressures to shape the learners' motivations. For this purpose, the study uses a mixed-method research design. It combines quantitative data collected through a structured questionnaire with qualitative accounts of the learners' experiences. Moreover, the study also aims to produce evidence that can inform and support motivation-based English language teaching in Pakistan. This leads to formulate the following research questions that guide the study.

1.1. Research Questions

1. What are the relative strengths of integrative and instrumental motivational orientations among BS English students in Pakistan?

2. To what extent are these motivational orientations associated with the learners' self-perceived achievement and persistence in learning English.

3. To what extent do the social, cultural, and familial factors shape the learners' motivational orientations toward learning English in Pakistan? The current study, by addressing these questions, contributes to the growing body of knowledge on L2 motivation in Pakistani context. The findings are relevant for English programs in Pakistani universities where the learners work in a complex linguistic environment. They provide recommendations for motivation-based language teaching in Pakistani universities. The study, utilizing complementary theories of Gardner and Dornyei, highlights the ways different forms of motivation relate to the learners' efforts to learn, their persistence, and their perceived progress. The amalgam of colonial history, aspiration for mobility, and institutional reliance on English makes these motivational patterns more important for BS English students. On broader level, the current study contributes to the theoretical discussions in the field of related research in SLA motivation. It also contributes practical guidance for curriculum design. In addition, it offers practical implications for language policy to support the learners' academic, linguistic, and professional development.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Motivation in Second Language Acquisition: Global Perspectives

Motivation is one of the most extensively studied topics in SLA. It is linked with L2 learners' achievement, their persistence, and their willingness to learn a language. Gardner (1985) defines motivation as a complex blend of attitudes, effort, and the desire to learn a second language. Many scholarly studies have concluded that the motivated learners show greater resilience, stronger self-regulated behavior, and better language outcomes (Noels, 2001; Masgoret & Gardner, 2003). In the early studies, motivation was treated as a fixed trait. The recent studies view motivation as a dynamic and context-based process. Dornyei (2001), in his process-based

approach, proposes that learners' motives change with the passage of time, and according to the learning conditions. After this, Dornyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System reshaped the concept of motivation. It linked motivation to the learner's imagined future selves. It includes the ideal L2 self, the ought to self, and learners' ongoing learning experiences. This framework of Dornyei has inspired a number of studies to explore the roles of identity, self-image, and social expectations in shaping learners' engagement with the target language (Ryan, 2009; Lamb, 2012). All these views show that motivation does not only exist within the individual learner. Instead, it grows out of wider psychological, cultural, and sociopolitical forces.

2.2 Integrative and Instrumental Motivation in Second Language Acquisition

Since the work of Gardner and Lambert, integrative and instrumental motivation have been widely utilized by the research scholars to explain the learners' reasons behind learning L2. Integrative motivation refers to a learner's desire to feel connected to the target language culture and community. Instrumental motivation refers to learning L2 for practical purpose. For instance, learning L2 to pass the exam, to secure good job, to get promotion, and for mobility (Gardner & Lambert, 1972). Most of the studies in this area have concluded that integrative motivation is stronger as compare to instrumental motivation. It aligns with deeper and longer lasting learning. Particularly, integrative motivation is stronger than instrumental motivation in the environments where the learners have interaction with L2 cultures and communities (Masgoret & Gardner, 2003). After this research phase of integrative and instrumental motivation, the scholars questioned this two-part distinction. They posed question whether this simple integrative-instrumental distinction fully captures the complexity of learners' motivation in this globalized world. English has become a lingua franca. The idea of a single target community is blurred. Now, a number of learners imagine a broad and international community rather than one tied only to the native speakers (Lamb, 2004;

Ushioda & Dörnyei, 2012). In many contexts, instrumental motives namely education, mobility, and job are dominant. Yet, it is also found that they coexist with affective and identity based orientations. Even if these orientations appear in different forms yet they work in a similar way to integrative motivation. They help learners to stay engaged and committed to learn the target language. In addition to this, it is very interesting and new dimension that in postcolonial and multilingual settings, integrative motivation may also include identification with the global English speaking networks, academic cultures, and online communities instead of the native speakers (Ryan, 2009). It suggests that integrative motivation is dynamic; it changes across regions. It is shaped by local histories, and status relations. Moreover, motivation is also influenced by the ways learners imagine their place within the wider English using world.

2.3 Motivation and English Learning in Postcolonial Countries

English language holds a very complex and conflicted status in postcolonial countries like Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka. It is used as a language of power, access, education, and international mobility. The research scholars in the related area have found that learners' motives, in such contexts, are influenced and shaped by structural inequalities, class ambitions, and ideologies of colonial language (Canagarajah, 2013; Norton, 2013). In such postcolonial contexts, English Language marks privilege and social mobility. This creates strong instrumental motivation. Yet it also carries symbolic value that affects identity, and status. Research studies from South and Southeast Asia indicate that learners, most of the times, have mixed motives. They learn English language to improve economic status. At the same time, they begin to develop cultural interest to join global communities (Lamb, 2012; Taguchi, Magid, & Papi, 2009). The findings of these studies question simple distinction between integrative and instrumental motivation. In this way, they highlight the need to consider the wider sociopolitical setting of English learning.

2.4 Research on Motivation in Pakistan

Although English language plays a very significant role in Pakistan's education system and professional domains, yet research in the area of L2 motivation remains limited. In Pakistani context, the existing studies deal with language policy (Rahman, 2005), English medium schooling (Rahman, 2010), and parental hopes for English (Manan, Khemlani, & Dumanig, 2017). These studies indicate that English is considered a gateway for social and economic mobility. They also highlight that the Pakistani learners also encounter external pressure for proficiency in English. This limited research suggests that Pakistani learners of English are motivated by local inequalities, schooling backgrounds, and family expectations. Pakistan's linguistic ecology is unique. Here, English is simultaneously a colonial legacy, a status symbol, and a global resource. In such a complex environment, it is not clear in what ways integrative motivation and instrumental motivation operate in university level students who specialize in English as a major subject. The recent age has seen a rise in IELTS, PTE, and overseas education. It has likely increased instrumental motives in adult students. Yet the link between these motives, their persistence, and their self-reported progress is still not well explored and understood.

2.5 Research Gap and Contribution of the Present Study

Global research studies agree that L2 motivation depends upon the context. It is shaped by the learners' social, educational, economic, cultural, and family environments. However, the complex environment of Pakistan where the learners have many overlapping reasons for learning English, remains underrepresented in the existing studies on L2 motivation. Most of the exiting studies deal with language policies, English medium schooling, and overall public attitude towards English language. There is little empirical work on university level English majors who learn English as a tool for mobility, and identity building, and as a field of academic and cultural engagement. Very little attention is paid to compare integrative and instrumental motivation. No existing study in

Pakistan has compared their relative link with effort, persistence, and self-perceived progress. The influence of social and family expectations on L2 motivation has also received limited critical attention. The present study fills these gaps. The current study examines L2 motivation among BS English students. The study uses mixed methods research design. Mixed method design helps to combine quantitative measures of instrumental motivation, integrative motivation, ought-to L2 motivation, and influence of social expectations on motivation with qualitative accounts of learners' lived experiences. The study analyses the coexistence of these motives. It aims to give a detailed and context-based picture of English learning motivation in Pakistan, a multilingual and postcolonial country. In this way, it links the theory of motivation with sociocultural, and economic conditions experienced by Pakistani English Majors. Therefore, this study also contributes to the current understanding of L2 motivation beyond widely studied contexts.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

Mixed-methods survey design is adopted to conduct the study. Quantitative and qualitative data are collected through a single questionnaire. This questionnaire integrates Likert-scale items with open-ended questions. Likert-scale items measure motivational orientations quantitatively. Open-ended questions are designed to elicit and explain learners' motivational orientations for learning English. They also help to collect information about the factors that support their engagement in the learning process. Qualitative data helps to explain the quantitative patterns (Creswell & Clark, 2011). This is a concurrent design with an embedded qualitative strand. This kind of embedded design is suitable to identify broad motivational patterns in sensitive and complex contexts that fixed response items may miss (Dörnyei, 2007). This design is selected because motivation is a complex construct. It facilitates to achieve better understanding of motivational orientations in Pakistani learners of English. According to Dörnyei (2007), this mixed approach is suitable for research in SLA where

various psychological, social, and contextual factors interact in complex ways.

The study utilizes Gardner's (1985) socio-educational model of L2 motivation and Dornyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System. These are the most influential theoretical frameworks in L2 motivation research. Gardner's model clearly distinguishes between integrative and instrumental motivation. It informs the comparative focus of the study on learners' reasons for studying English. Dornyei's L2 Motivational Self System aids to highlight the external factors like social and familial pressures that shape learners' motivation. These two frameworks guide the questionnaire. Their key constructs are operationalized into four quantitative subscales which measure different dimensions of motivation.

3.2. Participants

The participants are BS English students from the department of English of various affiliated colleges of University of the Punjab, Pakistan. Only English majors are focused because they learn English as a language skill, as an academic field, and as a future career pathway. Their motivation is expected to reflect a combination of practical orientations linked with exams, jobs, and mobility, as well as academic, identity-based, and cultural interest in language. A total of $N = 119$ students completed the questionnaire. They were enrolled in different semesters from one to eight. They came from different linguistic backgrounds. The participation was voluntary. They all provided informed consent before the collection of data.

3.3. Instrument

The data is collected through a questionnaire titled "Motivation for Learning English among BS English Students in Pakistan" (Appendix A). The instrument has three sections. Section A is designed to collect demographic information including eight items: age, gender, program, semester, home language, medium of instruction in Intermediate, interaction with IELTS, TOEFL or PTE, and experience of living or studying abroad. These eight items are coded from A1 to A8. Section B has 23 Likert scale items which are

rated on a five-point scale from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Section B is divided into four sub-categories. Subscale 'B.1 Instrumental Motivation (IM 1 - IM 8)' is designed to measure practical orientations for learning. These include reasons like examinations, higher education, employment, and mobility. Subscale 'B. 2 Integrative Motivation (IN 1 - IN 8)' is structured to measure interest in target language, its culture, global connection, and academic identity linked with English. Subscale 'B. 3 Ought-To-Motivation and Social Pressure (OT 1 - OT 4)' measures familial and social expectations and pressures. It is aligned with Dornyei's ought-to L2 self. Subscale 'B. 4 Self-Perceived Learning Outcomes (SP 1 - SP 3)' measures learners' engagement, effort, and progress. It serves as indicator of their achievement and persistence. All items are keyed positively. Higher scores show stronger agreement with the construct. Section C has three open-ended questions (C1 - C3). They are posed to contextualize qualitative findings. They ask learners about their main reasons for studying English, familial and social influences to learn English, and the maintenance of motivation during difficult time.

3.4. Procedure

The data was collected in December, 2025 through an online questionnaire created in Google Forms. First the permission was taken from the relevant departments. After that the link of questionnaire was shared with the BS English students. The participants were informed about the purpose of the study. They were also informed about the voluntary nature of the participation. Moreover, they were assured of the confidentiality. The online questionnaire form began with an informed consent. Only those students could proceed who agreed to participate. It required only 10 - 15 minutes. The responses were automatically recorded and stored in digital format. They were only accessible for the researcher.

3.5. Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis is conducted through SPSS. Only completed questionnaires are included (N = 119). Each subscale scores are calculated by taking the means of items. Overall patterns of motivation are measured through descriptive statistics: means and standard deviations. In order to compare the strengths of instrumental and integrative motivation, a paired t test is used. To explore the connection between motivational orientations and self-perceived outcomes, Pearson correlation coefficients are used. Cronbach's alpha is utilized to evaluate the internal consistency of the subscales.

The qualitative analysis deals with all three research questions. It investigates major motivational orientations, comparison between instrumental motivation and integrative motivation, persistence, supportive factors, and influence of external forces: social, cultural, and familial on motivation.

3.6. Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles are followed to conduct the study. Voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent are observed. All the participants are informed about the purpose of the study. Identifying information is not collected. The data is anonymized. It is stored securely. The data is only accessible to the researcher.

4. Results

This section deals with the findings of the study. It has two parts. In the first part, quantitative results are reported. These results address the research questions of the study. In the second part, qualitative findings are presented. These qualitative findings contextualize and elaborate the quantitative patterns. At the same time, they address all three research questions of the study.

4.1. Quantitative Results

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics of Motivational Orientations

Table 1. presents descriptive statistics for all four subscales of motivation. In general, the participants have showed high levels of motivation across all orientations. Instrumental motivation has the highest mean score (M = 4.14, SD = 0.81). Integrative motivation, with a little difference, is close behind in mean score (M = 4.06, SD = 0.80). Ought-to motivation, comparatively, showed lower mean score (M = 3.67, SD = 1.00). Yet it is still above the midpoint of the scale. The mean score of Self-perceived learning outcomes is also moderately high (M = 3.79, SD = 0.99). All four subscales demonstrate reliable internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.83 to 0.89. It indicates reliable measurement of the constructs.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Reliability of Motivation Subscales

Subscale	k_items	N	Mean	SD	Alpha
Instrumental Motivation (IM)	8	119	4.14	0.81	0.87
Integrative Motivation (IN)	8	119	4.06	0.80	0.89
Ought-to/ Social Pressure (OT)	4	119	3.67	1.00	0.83
Self-Perceived Outcomes (SP)	3	119	3.79	0.99	0.85

4.1.2. Comparison between Instrumental and Integrative Motivation (RQ 1)

Table 2. shows the difference between instrumental and integrative motivation. A paired-samples t-test is conducted to compare the strength of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation. According to the quantitative results, instrumental motivation (M = 4.14) is slightly higher than integrative motivation

(M = 4.06). However, this difference between the two orientations is not statistically significant $t(118) = 1.53, p = 0.128$. The effect size is small (Cohen’s $d_z = 0.14$). It indicates that instrumental and integrative motivation are almost similar in their strength among the students of BS English in the sample.

Table 2. Paired Comparison of Instrumental and Integrative Motivation

Comparison	N	Mean_IM	Mean_IN	Mean_Diff (IM-IN)	t	p	Cohen_dz
IM_mean vs IN_mean	119	4.139	4.059	0.080	1.534	0.128	0.141

Figure 2.

Comparison of Mean Instrumental and Integrative Motivation Scores (N = 119)

4.1.3. Association between Motivational Orientations and Self-Perceived Achievement and Persistence (RQ 2)

Pearson correlations are used to measure the relation between orientations of motivation and self-perceived learning outcomes. All the three orientations are found to be positively associated with self-perceived outcomes. As shown in Table 3, their correlations are statistically significant. Integrative motivation has the strongest

correlation ($r = 0.678, p < 0.001$). It is followed by instrumental motivation ($r = 0.616, p < 0.001$) and Ought-to motivation ($r = 0.603, p < 0.001$). According to these results, higher levels of motivation in the learners, regardless of orientations, are linked with their higher engagement, effort, and perceived progress in English learning.

Table 3. Correlations between Motivational Orientations and Self-Perceived Learning Outcomes

Predictor	r_with_SP	p_value
IM	0.616	< 0.001
IN	0.678	< 0.001
OT	0.603	< 0.001

Figure 3.

4.1.4. Social, Cultural, and Familial Influence (RQ 3)

The third subscale, Ought-to motivation and social pressure, measures social, cultural, and familial influences on motivational orientations of the learners. The mean score for this subscale (M = 3.67, SD = 1.00), as shown in table 1, suggests noticeable social, cultural, and familial pressures Figure 4.

that shape motivational orientations. Its self-perceived correlation with learning outcomes (r = 0.603, p < 0.001), as shown in table 3, is positively significant. It shows that these pressures are associated, meaningfully, with learners' engagement and persistence.

4.2. Qualitative Findings

The qualitative findings are extracted from the responses of BS English students to the three open-ended questions C1, C2, and C3 given in the section C of the questionnaire. The analysis of this qualitative section identifies repeated themes. These themes help to explain the learners' motivational orientations. They also help to highlight and explicate their persistence in

learning, and the social contexts that influence their learning of English.

4.2.1. Dominant Reasons for Studying English (RQ 1)

The learners' responses to C1 reveal their reasons for studying English. Most of them have several overlapping reasons, instead of one single reason. They have mentioned instrumental orientations

for their motivation like employment, higher education, CSS Exam, and international mobility. At the same time, many of them, also have mentioned that English is a source of enjoyment. They showed interest in English literature. They also pointed to a sense of academic identity as English major. For instance, one participant says: “English is an international language it has very higher scope for job career” (Participant 51, open-ended survey response, December 2025). It confirms that learners learn English for instrumental purposes. Another participant says: “My strongest reason for studying English is that I genuinely enjoy literature and linguistics” (Participant 55, open-ended survey response, December 2025). It supports integrative motivation. Overall, the responses suggest that instrumental and integrative motivations often appear together.

4.2.2. Motivation and Persistence (RQ 2)

The analysis of the learners’ responses to C3 shows various factors that they feel help them during the times of difficulty. The common themes found in their responses include future goals, personal interest in studying English, academic achievement, and a sense of responsibility towards their family expectations. The students gave responses like “when I feel tired or lose motivation thinking about my future goals and the support of my family and teachers help me continue studying English” (Participant 72, open-ended survey response, December 2025), “the beauty and charm of literature help me a lot” (Participant 109, open-ended survey response, December 2025), and “The silent expectations of my Parents” (Participant 95, open-ended survey response, December 2025). These responses highlight their sources of persistence in learning English. Their future goals, their interest in English literature, and their family expectations are supportive factors to stay motivated.

4.2.3. Social, Cultural, and Familial Influences (RQ 3)

The analysis of learners’ responses to C2 highlights a range of social, cultural and social influences on their motivation. One of the most

frequent themes is parental expectations. The parents expect their son or daughter to show high proficiency in English language. In most of the cases, it is particularly father’s expectation. It could be due to postcolonial history, and because English has become a status symbol in Pakistan. In addition, it is not only the parents rather other family members also influence the learners’ motivation. Some participants have mentioned their siblings and ‘cousins’ as influence on their motivation. For example, one participant, in the context of learning English, says: “my parents and siblings encourage me to study hard and achieve my goals” (Participant 15, open-ended survey response, December 2025). Moreover, Pakistani society gives high value to English. It has become a status symbol and fashion. Even, the people are judged by their proficiency in English language. The learners fear negative judgement and try their level best to learn English. The participant writes: “even I see many people have succeeded in their lives in my society so I also want to succeed in my life and achieve my goals” (Participant 15, open-ended survey response, December 2025). It suggests that English has achieved the status of guarantee to success in Pakistani society. Overall analysis of C3 responses suggest that learners’ motivational orientations are influenced by familial, cultural, and social expectations.

4.3. Integration of Quantitative Results and Qualitative Findings

The analysis of quantitative results and qualitative findings reveal that BS English students have high levels of instrumental and integrative motivation. There is no meaningful difference between the strengths of instrumental and integrative motivation. Instrumental motivation is slightly higher with a very minor difference. Moreover, all forms of motivational orientation are, positively, associated with persistence and self-perceived achievement. The analysis of qualitative data shows that learners’ motivational orientations are influenced by practical purposes, and personal interest. Their motivation is also shaped by cultural, social, and familial expectations.

5. Discussion

The current study investigated motivational orientations in BS English students, in Pakistan. The study compared the strengths of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation. Moreover, it examined their association with persistence, and self-perceived achievement. It also explored the social, familial, and cultural influences on learners' motivation. The overall quantitative and qualitative results accentuate high levels of motivation, and coexisting orientations. The learners' motivational profile is marked by social pressure, personal goals, and identity based interests.

The quantitative results show high scores in all forms of motivation. Both instrumental motivation ($M = 4.14$) and integrative motivation ($M = 4.06$) are strongly supported by the respondents. It suggests that learners in BS English have overlapping motivational orientations. They do not appear to rely on a single motive. Their motivational patterns are shaped by practical aims, and personal investment, at the same time. The qualitative findings support the patterns found in quantitative results. The respondents have mentioned their plans for employment, CSS Exam, further education, and international mobility. At the same time, they have also mentioned their enjoyment of English language and literature. These accounts reflect motivational overlap. On one hand, the responses reflect Gardner's (2005) instrumental and integrative motivation. On the other hand, they also reflect a broader view point that motivation is shaped by learners' experiences and aspirations.

In the context of research question number one, the comparison between integrative and instrumental motivation shows no significant difference. Instrumental motivation is slightly higher than integrative motivation. But the difference is not statistically significant that is $t(118) = 1.53$, $p = 0.128$, Cohen's $d_z = 0.14$. This exploration is very important because in postcolonial contexts motivation is often instrumental (Canagarajah, 2013). The findings of the current study present a balanced picture. Both motivational orientations appear to be similarly strong in BS English students of Pakistan. One

interpretation could be that they get enrolled in the programs of English language and literature for instrumental purposes. But with the passage of time, and exposure, they begin to develop personal enjoyment, and identification with English language and literature. It resembles integrative motivation. English holds practical as well as personal value in Pakistan. This aligns with the studies that argue that integrative motivation can take various forms (Ryan, 2009; Lamb, 2012). It may involve ties with global communities, and academic identities. It may link with imagined futures instead of direct interaction with native speakers.

In the context of research question number two, the results of correlation between all forms of motivation and self-perceived outcomes show positive links. The integrative motivation has the strongest correlation ($r = 0.678$, $p < 0.001$). This is followed by instrumental motivation ($r = 0.616$, $p < 0.001$) and Ought-to motivation ($r = 0.603$, $p < 0.001$). According to the given results, the higher levels of motivation in the learners are connected with their higher engagement, effort, and perceived progress in learning English. The relatively strong correlation between integrative motivation and outcomes is important to note. It indicates that the learners' interest, enjoyment, identity investment, and a sense of connection with English language and literature is connected to their engagement, effort and persistence. This is aligned with the concept of Rod Ellis (2015) that intrinsic motivation is more helping to sustain persistence as compared to instrumental motivation. However, instrumental motivation has also strong correlation with outcomes. It suggests the importance of pragmatic goals. They are also significant drivers of effort, and persistence. The analysis of qualitative responses, on persistence, complements these quantitative patterns. The learners continue due to their future plans and goals. At the same time, they take interest in English language and literature. Many of the learners don't give up due to their sense of responsibility, and due to cultural, social and familial expectations. As a whole, quantitative results and qualitative findings, on persistence,

reveal that it is supported by an amalgam of future goals, personal interest, and social obligation.

Third research question deals with the extent to which cultural, social, and familial factors influence motivational orientations. The Ought-to or social pressure subscale ($M = 3.67$) shows a clear presence of external pressure. It also has a strong correlation with outcomes ($r = 0.603$, $p < 0.001$). It highlights the link that lies between external pressure and learner's persistence. The qualitative data complements these quantitative results. Qualitative accounts help to explain these external pressures. The students of BS English report parental expectations, fear of social judgement, and the great emphasis on English in Pakistan. These align with Dornyei's (2005) Ought-to L2 self. According to this concept, expectations and obligations shape motivation. In addition to this, it is important to note that external pressures are not always negative. They create stress but they are also supportive to commitment. Particularly, it is supportive in the settings of social and academic rewards. The combined interpretations of quantitative and qualitative data accentuate that external pressures are central to the learners' motivational environment.

5.1. Pedagogical Implications

The qualitative results, quantitative findings and their interpretation have several implications for motivation-based teaching in Pakistan. Instrumental and integrative motivations are strong in Pakistan. Instructions may be more effective when they incorporate both the dimensions of motivation. The course content may be linked to the students' practical goals. It may improve their motivation to stay engaged in learning English. Moreover, in the Pakistani context, social pressure is very influential. The classroom environment should communicate expectations in a careful way. Supportive norms may reduce the fear of judgement. They may normalize the mistakes. It may maintain confidence level of the learners. Furthermore, the advising systems may make the students' future-oriented goals more actionable. Guidance on scholarships, research opportunities, CSS exams, teaching careers, and postgraduate options may

facilitate the learners to turn instrumental aims into clear plans. Similarly, the supportive tasks that strengthen academic identity may enhance integrative persistence. These supportive tasks may include research activities, reading circles, and discussions, particularly peer discussions.

5.2. Limitations of the Study and Future Research Directions

The current study acknowledges several limitations that point towards significant options for future research. In the first place, the study relies on learners' self-reported learning outcomes. It does not look at their direct performance. Future research studies may include proficiency tests or course grades. It may help the researchers to check whether similar patterns appear in objective measures. In the second place, the participants belong to BS English programs in affiliated colleges of University of the Punjab, Pakistan. This particular sample may limit generalization to other settings. In the third place, the open-ended, qualitative, responses were brief. Follow up interviews, after quantitative phase, could produce more rich data to complement and confirm quantitative results.

6. Conclusion

The current research study investigated motivational orientations in BS English students in Pakistan. It explored the relative strengths of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation. Moreover, it dealt with the correlations between motivational orientations and self-perceived persistence and achievements. The study also traced the influence of cultural, familial, and social factors on motivation. The researcher utilized mixed methods design. Quantitative measures are complemented and confirmed by qualitative accounts of the learners. The quantitative results and qualitative findings, together, highlight high motivation in BS English students. Instrumental and integrative motivations are similarly strong, with a little difference. Instrumental motivation is slightly higher than integrative motivation. This difference is statistically non-significant. Both the orientations work alongside. They don't oppose

each other. This exploration challenges a well-established idea that Pakistani learners of English are driven by utilitarian goals. The learners take personal interest and build academic identity. They enjoy learning English and plan pragmatic aims. Furthermore, the strong correlation between all forms of motivation and self-perceived learning outcomes indicates that motivation, in many shapes, reinforces persistence and engagement in learning English. The findings of the study also accentuate the importance of external factors like cultural, social, and familial expectations. The Ought-to motivation, in quantitative as well as in qualitative data, reveals that motivation does not come out of nowhere; it is shaped by social forces. These external forces amalgamate with learners' own aims, and identities and strengthen motivation.

The current study reinforces a view that L2 motivation is multidimensional. It is shaped by context. The results align with Gardner's instrumental-integrative distinction and Dörnyei's socially constructed motivational selves. The findings have pedagogical implications in Pakistani context. The classroom environments should amalgamate pragmatic orientations with personal interest. It would foster confidence in the learners of English.

Future researchers could utilize the current study and advance the findings. They may use longitudinal designs, objective achievement measures, or detailed interviews. It could accentuate that motivation evolves over time and learners respond differently to external pressures at different stages. It would enrich the understanding of motivation.

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